

HOW TO PROPERLY CARE BEHIND THE ORAL CAVITY

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The task of individual oral hygiene is to remove microbial plaque, including conditionally pathogenic microflora of cariogenic microorganisms, such as streptococci and lactobacilli (Lukinykh L.M., 1998, 2004). Such microorganisms use carbohydrates for nutrition and construction of dental plaque.

The end product of dental plaque is organic acids, which change the pH of the oral environment in an acidic direction. Individual oral hygiene can change the qualitative and quantitative composition of the oral microflora. For this it is necessary to reduce the consumption of carbohydrates, change the diet nutrition, use fluoride, sanitize the oral cavity. If you comply with all of the above conditions, it is possible to significantly reduce the prevalence and intensity of dental diseases among the population. Regular, timely and proper oral hygiene is capable of ensuring 85–90% dental health.

Personal oral hygiene is recommended for everyone. A modern person (in the absence of oral hygiene) can lose all his teeth, even the healthiest ones by nature and at a very young age.

Archaeological excavations have repeatedly proven that even in young people 18–35 years old, teeth are either completely destroyed or were absent from the jaws. This confirms that it is impossible to exaggerate the importance of oral hygiene and the success of hygiene will be successful only if hygiene is performed regularly and correctly. Proper and regular oral hygiene is dental care morning and evening, and throughout the day.

A toothbrush is a more ancient device. Teeth cleaning sticks have been found during excavations in ancient Etruria and Egypt. Currently, in China and the Arab world they use the so-called Miswak is a stick made from arak wood that, when chewed, breaks into pieces many fibers, resembling a brush.

Archaeological finds in ancient Egyptian burials indicate that ancient people used wooden sticks as toothbrushes. Indian medicine (Ayurveda) used the neem tree for dental brushes. The tip of the twig was chewed until soft. The first toothbrush resembling a modern brush was invented in China (in the late 1400s) and was made from hog hair attached to a bamboo stick. William Addis (UK) designed the first commercially available toothbrush in 1780.

In those days, brushes were only available to rich people. Thanks to nylon, it became possible to make their production mass. In 1938, natural bristles (made from animal hair) were replaced on synthetic fibers, mainly nylon (DuPont).

During the time of Ivan the Terrible in Russia, dental “brooms” were in use - sticks with a tuft of bristles at the end, which the boyars used after meals. Peter I ordered the boyars to brush their teeth with crushed chalk and a wet cloth. Another popular method of cleaning teeth was also known: coals (for example, from birch wood) whiten teeth perfectly, but after such cleaning the mouth should be rinsed especially thoroughly. The toothbrush in its current form has been around in Germany for many years ago - the main factory for the production of toothbrushes opened.

These days, the oral hygiene industry is evolving and each company is offering different toothbrush designs. Let's just erect a monument to the brush! Which, by the way, was done! Monument toothbrush was installed in 1983 in the German town of Krefeld.

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